

Terpenoids. Part XI. Unambiguous Synthesis of β -terpineol and 1(7), 8-*p*-Menthadiene

O. P. Vig, Khushi Lall Matta, Gurdip Singh, and Inder Raj

β -Terpineol and 1(7), 8-*p*-menthadiene have been synthesised by an application of the Wittig reaction with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide on 1-methyl-4-acetylcyclohexan-1-ol and 1-keto-4-acetylcyclohexanone, respectively.

β -Terpineol, a monocyclic monoterpene alcohol, is a constituent of the commercial terpineol¹. The formulation (I) has been assigned to the alcohol on the basis of physical and chemical studies¹ and synthetic evidence².

Perkin's preparation of β -terpineol from an intermediary bromo-ketone (A), however, resulted, in the dehydrobromination sequence, in a mixture of 4-isopropenylcyclohexanone (B) and the 4-isopropylidene isomer (C).

The present investigation records a clean synthesis of β -terpineol which is free from the ambiguity associated with the earlier attempt².

Ethyl 4,2'-ethoxycarbonyl-ethyl-5,5-ethylenedioxyhexanoate³ (II), the starting material in the present scheme, was subjected to Dieckmann's condensation when 2-ethoxycarbonyl-4,1',1'-ethylenedioxyethylcyclohexanone (III) was obtained in 30% yield.

Alkaline hydrolysis of the β -keto-ester (III), followed by decarboxylation with copper powder, furnished in 80% yield 4,1',1'-ethylenedioxyethylcyclohexanone (IV). The ketal-ketone (IV) showed IR absorption peaks⁴ at 1720cm^{-1} (-C=O), 1050cm^{-1} (ketal). The semicarbazone of (IV) afforded colorless needles from ethanol, m.p. 215° . The compound

1. Pinder, "The Chemistry of the Terpenes", Chapman and Hall Ltd., London, 1960, p. 51.
2. Perkin jun., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 870.
3. Suzuki, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1961, **82**, 730; *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, **57**, 16422.
4. Cross, "Introduction to Practical I. R. Spectroscopy", Butterworths Scientific Publications, London, 1960, pp. 58-63.

(IV) on treatment with methylmagnesium iodide furnished 1-methyl-4, 1', 1'-ethylenedioxyethylcyclohexan-1-ol (V) in 86% yield. The ketal-carbinol (V) on deketalisation with HCl in acetone solution⁵ furnished 1-methyl-4-acetylcyclohexan-1-ol (VI) in 83% yield.

The compound (VI) showed characteristic IR peaks⁴ at 1720 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1150, 3460 cm^{-1} (-OH), and 1380 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{Me}$).

The hydroxyketone (VI), when submitted to Wittig's reaction⁶ with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide, afforded 1-methyl-4-isopropenylcyclohexan-1-ol (I) in 70% yield.

The alcohol (I) was characterised through its IR absorption spectrum which showed peaks⁴ at 1150, 3460 cm^{-1} (-OH), 888 cm^{-1} ($\text{R}_1 \text{R}_2 \text{C}=\text{CH}_2$), 1380 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{Me}$).

1 (7), 8-*p*-Menthadiene, which does not occur in nature and is one of the products⁷ from the pyrolysis of β -pinene, has been given the constitution (VIII) on the basis of analytical and chemical studies and its preparation⁸. The present synthetic route records an unambiguous synthesis of 1(7),8-*p*-menthadiene.

4, 1', 1'-Ethylenedioxyethylcyclohexanone (IV), on deketalisation with hydrochloric acid in acetone solution⁵, provided 4-acetylcyclohexanone (VII) in 79% yield. The diketone (VII) was characterised through its IR absorption which showed a peak⁴ at 1720 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$). The compound (VII) furnished 2, 4-DNP, m.p. 200°.

5. Church and Ireland, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 18.

6. Greenwald *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1963, **28**, 1128.

7. Steinbach *et al.*, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 959.

8. Webb and Bain, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4279.

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The diketone (VII), when submitted to the Wittig reaction with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide, afforded 1-methylene-4-isopropenylcyclohexane (VIII) in 75% yield. The synthetic hydrocarbon (VIII) showed IR absorption peak⁴ at 890 cm^{-1} (strong) ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{CH}_2}$), and other peaks at 1650, 1200, 1088, 1035, 1000, 955, 825, and 810 cm^{-1} , comparable to the values reported in the literature⁷.

*EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 4,2'-Ethoxycarbonylethyl-5,5-ethylenedioxyhexanoate (II) was prepared according to the procedure laid down in the literature³.

4,1',1'-Ethylenedioxyethylcyclohexanone (IV).—To sodium dust (5.5 g.) in dry benzene (100 ml) was added the ketal-diester (II) (27.5 g.) and the contents were refluxed on a water bath for 12 hr. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice-cold HCl (calc. amount); the organic material was taken in benzene-ether mixture and washed with water. The solvent was removed and a small amount of the viscous mass was distilled for analysis; b. p. $150\text{--}55^\circ/3\text{ mm}$, $n_D^{21.5}$ 1.4820. (Found: C, 60.86; H, 7.9. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 60.92; H, 7.87%). It developed a violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

The crude β -keto-ester (III) (8.5 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of KOH (7.0 g.), methanol (60 ml), and water (40 ml) for 10 hr. Methanol was removed under reduced pressure and to the residue were added sufficient cold water and ether (100 ml). The reaction mixture was neutralised with ice-cold HCl and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The organic layer was washed thoroughly with ice-cold water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residual oil was distilled under vacuum with copper powder to yield 4.9 g. (80.2%) of (IV); b. p. $115^\circ/3\text{--}4\text{ mm}$, n_D^{20} 1.4750. (Found: C, 65.40; H, 8.8. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 65.19; H, 8.75%). The *semicarbazone*, prepared by the usual manner and recrystallised from dilute ethanol, melted at 215° . (Found: N, 17.42. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires N, 17.80%).

1-Methyl-4,1',1'-ethylenedioxyethylcyclohexan-1 ol (V).—To the Grignard reagent, prepared from magnesium (0.45 g.) and methyl iodide (3.2 g.) in dry ether (20 ml), was

*Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalyses by Mr. B. N. Anand, Microanalyst, Panjab University Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. IR spectra were recorded on Beckman I. R.-5 with sodium chloride optics, using a thin film.

added dropwise a solution of compound (IV) (3.3 g.) in dry ether (10 ml) in the cold. After keeping the mixture overnight, it was refluxed for 1 hr. (water bath), cooled, decomposed with a saturated solution of ammonium chloride, and worked up in the usual way. The solvent was removed and the ketal-carbinol (V) was distilled under vacuum; b.p. 125-30°/5 mm, yield 3.1 g. (86.4%), $n_D^{19.5}$ 1.4790. IR absorption peaks at 1150, 3460 cm^{-1} (-OH), 1050 cm^{-1} (ketal). (Found: C, 66.00; H, 10.20. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 65.97; H, 10.07%).

1-Methyl-4-acetylcyclohexan-1-ol (VI).—The above ketal-carbinol (V) (2.0 g.) was deketalised with a mixture of acetone (40 ml) and HCl (11.5 ml, 10%) at the room temperature. The contents after dilution with brine (30 ml) were worked up in the usual manner to provide the keto-carbinol (VI, 1.3 g.) as a colorless oil, b.p. 100-105°/3-4mm, yield 83.3%. $n_D^{19.5}$ 1.4700. (Found: C, 69.50; H, 10.50. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 69.19; H, 10.32%).

1-Methyl 4-isopropenylcyclohexan-1-ol (I).—A solution of sodium methylsulphinyl carbanion was prepared under nitrogen from sodium hydride (0.28 g.) and dimethyl sulphoxide (3 ml). The solution was cooled in an ice-cold water bath and stirred during addition of methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (2.3 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (6 ml) till the reddish colour of the methylenephosphorane appeared. After stirring at the room temperature for 15 min., the keto-carbinol (VI) (0.9 g.) in THF (7.5 ml) was added and the stirring continued for 2 hr. at 50°. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured on cold water (15 ml). The organic layer was taken up in petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) and washed thrice with cold water. After removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled in vacuum to afford the carbinol (I) (0.62 g.) in 70.4% yield; b.p. 85-89°/4-5 mm, $n_D^{19.5}$ 1.4740 (lit.⁸ n_D^{20} 1.4747). (Found: C, 78.09; H, 11.58. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ requires C, 77.86; H, 11.76%).

4-Acetylcyclohexanone (VII).—To a solution of the ketone (IV) (1.5 g.) in acetone (20 ml) was added HCl (5 ml, 10%) and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand at the room temperature for 2 hr. with occasional shaking. The contents after dilution with brine (15 ml) were worked up in the usual way when the diketone (VII) distilled at 115-20°/10mm; yield 0.9 g. (79%), $n_D^{19.5}$ 1.4495. (Found: C, 68.69; H, 8.80. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 68.54; H, 8.63%). The 2,4-DNP was prepared by sulphuric acid method in cold and recrystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 200°. (Found: N, 22.00. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6\text{N}_8$ requires N, 22.39%).

1-Methylene-4-isopropenylcyclohexane (VIII).—Methylenephosphorane was prepared under nitrogen atmosphere from sodium hydride (0.21 g.), dimethyl sulphoxide (2.5 ml), and methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (1.7g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (5.0 ml) in the manner of (I). To this was added the diketone (VII) (0.75 g.) in THF (6 ml). After working up as in (I), the oil was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish (VIII); yield 0.55 g. (75.5%), b.p. 50°/2-3mm, n_D^{20} 1.4700 (lit.⁷ n_D^{25} 1.4714. (Found: C, 88.0; H, 11.65. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}$ requires C, 88.16; H, 11.84%).

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